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RENEWABLE ENERGY RESEARCH IN AREAS UZBEKISTAN: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

¹Sorimsokov Uchqun Soatboy o‘g‘li, ² Olimov Orif Nosirovich

^{1,2}Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

uchqunsarimsoqov112@gmail.com

Annotation: In the world practice, the use of non-traditional energy sources is expanding, but in Uzbekistan this process is developing very slowly. The country's economy is built on the use of mainly hydrocarbon raw materials, which are mostly used for domestic needs. At the same time, natural gas is exported in ever-increasing volumes. At the same time, Uzbekistan has a great potential for alternative energy sources, which, according to experts, are three times higher than the resources of organic non-renewable fuel. The article discusses the possibilities of efficient use of alternative energy in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Wind Generator, Alternative Energy, Wind Power, Solar Energy, Energy Efficiency.

Introduction

In The use of non-traditional and renewable energy sources in the fuel and energy industry is an urgent task of the world energy industry. One of their main types, which is environmentally friendly and affordable, is the energy of solar radiation. The use of non-traditional and renewable energy sources in the fuel and energy industry is an urgent task of the world energy industry[1].

One of their main types, which is environmentally friendly and affordable, is the energy of solar radiation. Uzbekistan has favorable climatic conditions for the use of solar energy, the energy potential of which is 98.5 percent of all renewable energy sources combined, so its use is relevant both for the purpose of ensuring energy security and improving the social and living conditions of the population. At the same time, the possibility of preserving hydrocarbon fuel reserves for future generations and mitigating the environmental situation in the country is of no small importance [2-4].The main components of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan are solar, hydraulic, wind and geothermal energy, as well as biomass energy. According to the results of the conducted assessments, the technical potential of renewable energy sources in the Republic of Uzbekistan

is 180 million tons of oil equivalent, which is more than three times higher than its annual demand for energy resources[5].

The most prepared area of large-scale use of solar energy in the country's economy, as well as in the whole world, is its conversion to low-potential heat using flat solar collectors for heating water and its use in hot water supply systems for residential, municipal and social facilities. It should be noted that in low-rise residential buildings, which make up 76 percent of the total housing stock, out of the total natural gas consumption (15,100 million cubic meters), only about 3,000 million cubic meters are spent on hot water supply. Analysis and generalization of world experience in this area show that the actual scale of solar energy use in hot water systems, all other things being equal, depends on the technical and economic indicators of their main element—a flat solar water heating collector, the scale of production and use of which is constantly growing worldwide. It should be noted that considerable experience has been accumulated in the field of thermal conversion and solar energy use in Uzbekistan, and a sufficient scientific and technical reserve has been created.

Materials and methods

The extensive use of alternative energy sources is in line with the priority objectives of each country and the tasks of energy security and is one of the rapidly developing directions of the energy sector.

Certain works are being carried out on the development of renewable energy sources in the Republic, first of all on the use of the potential of hydropower. Energy is currently the highest priority area of engineering science, which deals with the transformation, transmission, storage and use of energy. The history of the civilization of all mankind is connected with the consumption of energy of various types. The main feature of the modern world is an increase in energy consumption in all spheres of public life[10-12].

In the field of development and use of non-traditional renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan, the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures for the further development of alternative energy sources" dated March 1, 2013, which became a program document in the planning and implementation of fundamental and applied research aimed at expanding the use of alternative energy sources, primarily solar[13].

The environment is polluted because of the harmful gases coming out of the power and heat stations and internal combustion engines that use organic types of fuel. Over the years, it has been undermining the ozone layer as a result of the massive release of the remains of harmful substances into the atmosphere, while on earth there is a global energy deficit. As a result, the change in the world's climate, the decrease in energy resources are closely connected with the

problem of food scarcity, which puts enormous problems before humanity[20].

An increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere leads to global climate change and the formation of a greenhouse effect, and as a result, to possible environmental disasters. Most types of renewable energy sources (RES) are derived from solar exposure. Such as the appearance of winds due to changes in temperature and atmospheric pressure, the formation of water resources due to evaporation from the seas and oceans[10].

According to world energy data, the ratio of energy sources in global electricity production in 2018 was as follows: renewable energy sources(RES) 26%, including the share of solar energy 3%, the share of wind energy 6%, other types of RES 17%, traditional energy sources (TES) – 74% .

Consumption and demand for electricity both around the world and in the Republic of Uzbekistan is growing every year. The reason for this is the intensive development of industry, manufacturing, construction and other sectors of the country, the growth of settlements and infrastructure facilities that consume electricity. The specific share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the total volume of electricity generation in Uzbekistan is currently 10%.

The remaining 90% of electricity comes from traditional energy sources (TES) .

In this regard, the development and widespread use of solar energy in Uzbekistan are more relevant and promising.

There are various technological methods for using and converting solar energy, the use of which can produce a sufficiently large amount of heat and electricity.

The use of solar energy can be carried out by the following main installations and methods:

- Solar water heating installations (collectors) in which the heat carrier, water, air is heated. Such installations are widely used for heating and hot water supply.
- Direct conversion of solar radiation into electricity by means of photovoltaic converters (PVS) built on the basis of semiconductor materials.

All these technologies, power plants for the use and conversion of solar energy can be successfully applied in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan. [10-12].

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